

Viscosity and activation parameters of viscous flow of L-arginine in aqueous D-maltose monohydrate system over the temperature range (298.15 to 308.15) K

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Abstract : Viscosities of L-arginine (0.025 to 0.2 mol kg⁻¹) in varying concentrations of aqueous D-maltose monohydrate (0 to 6 mass % of maltose monohydrate in water) have been measured at different temperatures, viz. 298.15 K, 303.15 K and 308.15 K. The experimental results are analysed in accordance with viscosity *B*-coefficients, viscosity *B*-coefficients of transfer, *B*_{tr}, and variation of *B* with temperature, *dB/dT*. The Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^\ddagger$, as well as per mole of solute, $\Delta\mu_2^\ddagger$, along with activation enthalpy, ΔH_2^\ddagger , and activation entropy, ΔS_2^\ddagger , using different concentrations of D-maltose monohydrate in aqueous medium are also evaluated using Feakin's transition-state theory. The results are discussed in terms of intermolecular interactions and that the solute acts as structure maker in the solvent system under study.

Keywords : Viscosity, L-arginine, D-maltose monohydrate, viscosity *B*-coefficients, activation parameters.

Introduction

The polyhydroxy compounds play a very important role in stabilizing the native conformations of proteins/enzymes¹⁻³. Saccharides are widely distributed in various forms of life as essential moieties of glycoproteins, glycolipids, nucleic acids and polysaccharides. Because of conformational flexibility, saccharides play significant role in many biological processes such as signalling, cell-cell recognition and molecular and cellular communication⁴⁻⁶. The stabilization of native conformations of proteins has been related to various non-covalent interactions like hydrogen bonding, electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions^{7,8}. The study of these interactions provides important insight into the conformational stability and folding/unfolding of globular proteins⁹ and are found implicated in several biochemical and physiological processes of a living cell¹⁰⁻¹². The complex conformational and configurational factors determining the structure of proteins in sugar solution makes the study of protein-sugar interactions difficult. Since amino acids are the model components of protein molecules, their transport properties in aqueous and aqueous saccharide solutions provide

valuable information on solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions which are useful in studying the stability of proteins. Keeping this in mind, a number of researchers have studied the amino acid sugar interactions by employing the viscometric technique. Nain and Pal¹³ have determined the behaviour of L-methionine in aqueous D-glucose and L-threonine in aqueous glucose solutions at different temperatures using viscometric method. Pal and Chauhan¹⁴ have studied the viscosities of (i) diglycine in aqueous saccharide solutions, (ii) glycine, L-alanine, L-valine and L-leucine in aqueous lactose solutions and (iii) glyglyglycine in aqueous sucrose and fructose solutions, all at different temperatures. The viscosity of L-serine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine in aqueous D-glucose solutions at 298.15 K was reported by Palani and Geetha¹⁵. Ali *et al.* have measured the viscometric behaviour of glycine, DL-alanine, L-serine and DL-valine in aqueous D-glucose solution at different temperatures¹⁶. Zhao *et al.* have studied the viscosity *B*-coefficients of arginine in aqueous D-glucose and sucrose solutions¹⁷. Riyazuddeen and Usmani have reported the viscosities for L-alanine, L-threonine and L-glycylglycine in aqueous D-glucose and

D-sucrose solutions in a wide temperature range¹⁸. Nain *et al.* have also studied the viscometric studies of (L-arginine + D-xylose/L-arabinose + water) solutions at different temperatures¹⁹; L-histidine in water + sucrose solutions at different temperatures²⁰. Bhat *et al.* have recorded the transfer of some amino acids and peptides from water to aqueous glucose and sucrose solutions²¹. Rajagopal and Johnson have determined the viscosity coefficient and activation parameters of viscous flow of a homologous amino acids in aqueous xylose solutions²² whereas Khanuja have determined viscometric study of interactions of amino acids in aqueous sucrose solutions at different temperatures²³. However, to the best of our knowledge, no approach has been made on viscometric properties of L-arginine (positively charged side chain) in aqueous-maltose monohydrate at different temperatures.

Thus, the present work focuses on viscosity behaviour of different molalities of L-arginine (solute) as a consequence of varying concentration of maltose monohydrate (co-solute) in aqueous medium (solvent) at 298.15, 303.15 and 308.15 K. Using this data, the viscosity B -coefficients, viscosity B -coefficients of transfer, activation Gibbs free energies and other related thermodynamic activation parameters of viscous flow have been calculated followed by their interpretation on the basis of solute-solvent as compared to solute-solute interactions.

Experimental

D-Maltose monohydrate (abbreviated as MM) and L-arginine (both having a reported mass fraction purity of > 0.998) were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (India) and used as such. The aqueous-saccharide solutions (0 to 6 mass % of MM in water) were prepared using triple distilled water with specific conductance less than 1×10^{-6} S cm⁻¹. This was used as solvent to prepare L-arginine solution of eight different molalities (ranging from 0.025 m to 0.200 m). An electronic single pan five digit analytical balance (Mettler; Model AE-240) with a precision of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-5}$ g was used for weighing. All the solutions were prepared with utmost care and stored in special airtight bottles to avoid the exposure of solution to air and evaporation. The possible error in the mole fraction is calculated to be less than $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$. The viscosity of the solutions was measured by using Ubbelohde type sus-

pended level viscometer. In order to avoid the thermal fluctuation of solutions in viscometer, the solution was allowed to stand for about half an hour in a thermostatic water bath. The time of flow was noticed using an electronic watch with the resolution of 0.01 s. The average of at least five readings reproducible within 0.1 s was used as the final efflux time. The uncertainty in viscosity measurements was within $\pm 1 \times 10^{-6}$ N s m⁻². The temperature of the solution was maintained to an accuracy of ± 0.02 K in an electronic controlled thermostatic water bath (Model : TIC-4000N, Thermotech, India). The density of solutions was measured using vibrating tube density meter (Model : DMA 4500 M, Anton Paar, Austria) with an uncertainty of ± 0.00005 g cm⁻³. Before each series of measurement, it was calibrated using triple distilled water and dry air at atmospheric pressure. The temperature was automatically kept constant within ± 0.03 K with the help of in-built peltier system.

Results and discussion

The experimental values for viscosity and density of L-arginine in aqueous and aqueous-MM medium as a function of molality of amino acid and temperature are listed in the Table 1 and graphically shown in Fig. 1. The viscosity of L-arginine in water as also in aqueous-MM increases as the concentration of solute increases, but decreases with rise of temperature. The relative viscosity of solution is obtained using the following equation²⁴.

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Am^{1/2} + Bm \quad (1)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity of the solution (L-arginine + aqueous-MM), η and η_0 are the viscosities of solution and solvent (aqueous-MM), respectively. The Falkenhagen coefficient A accounts for the ion-ion or solute-solute interactions, while B is the Jones-Dole coefficient. The later is an empirical term which measures the size, shape and charge effects as well as the structural effect induced by solute-solvent interactions^{25,26}. The Falkenhagen coefficient is found to be much smaller in magnitude as compared to Jones-Dole coefficient indicating the presence of weak solute-solute interactions and hence, can be considered negligible in case of non-electrolytes²⁷. The values of B -coefficients, obtained using a

Table 1. Density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of solutions of different molalities of L-arginine in water and aqueous-MM solutions at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	T (K)					
	298.15		303.15		308.15	
	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (N s m ⁻²) $\times 10^3$	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (N s m ⁻²) $\times 10^3$	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (N s m ⁻²) $\times 10^3$
L-Arginine + water						
0.000	997.07	0.8903	995.68	0.7973	994.07	0.7190
0.025	998.35	0.9005	996.96	0.8053	995.35	0.7257
0.050	999.63	0.9108	998.24	0.8133	996.63	0.7324
0.075	1000.91	0.9210	999.52	0.8214	997.91	0.7391
0.100	1002.19	0.9313	1000.80	0.8294	999.19	0.7459
0.125	1003.47	0.9416	1002.08	0.8375	1000.47	0.7527
0.150	1004.75	0.9519	1003.36	0.8456	1001.75	0.7594
0.175	1006.03	0.9623	1004.64	0.8537	1003.03	0.7662
0.200	1007.31	0.9727	1005.92	0.8618	1004.31	0.7730
L-Arginine + 2% aqueous-MM						
0.000	1004.26	0.9355	1003.45	0.8343	1002.47	0.7459
0.025	1005.50	0.9486	1004.69	0.8450	1003.71	0.7549
0.050	1006.74	0.9618	1005.93	0.8556	1004.95	0.7639
0.075	1007.98	0.9750	1007.17	0.8663	1006.19	0.7729
0.100	1009.22	0.9883	1008.41	0.8771	1007.43	0.7820
0.125	1010.46	1.0015	1009.65	0.8878	1008.67	0.7911
0.150	1011.70	1.0148	1010.89	0.8986	1009.91	0.8002
0.175	1012.94	1.0282	1012.13	0.9094	1011.15	0.8093
0.200	1014.18	1.0415	1013.37	0.9202	1012.39	0.8183
L-Arginine + 4% aqueous-MM						
0.000	1011.64	0.9838	1010.59	0.8711	1009.41	0.7698
0.025	1012.86	1.0008	1011.81	0.8852	1010.63	0.7815
0.050	1014.08	1.0179	1013.03	0.8993	1011.85	0.7932
0.075	1015.30	1.0350	1014.25	0.9134	1013.07	0.8049
0.100	1016.52	1.0521	1015.47	0.9276	1014.29	0.8167
0.125	1017.74	1.0693	1016.69	0.9418	1015.51	0.8284
0.150	1018.96	1.0865	1017.91	0.9560	1016.73	0.8402
0.175	1020.18	1.1037	1019.13	0.9702	1017.95	0.8521
0.200	1021.40	1.1209	1020.35	0.9844	1019.17	0.8638
L-Arginine + 6% aqueous-MM						
0.000	1020.59	1.0365	1019.32	0.9112	1017.91	0.7962
0.025	1021.78	1.0580	1020.51	0.9290	1019.10	0.8113
0.050	1022.97	1.0796	1021.70	0.9469	1020.29	0.8264
0.075	1024.16	1.1012	1022.89	0.9647	1021.48	0.8415
0.100	1025.35	1.1229	1024.08	0.9827	1022.67	0.8567
0.125	1026.54	1.1446	1025.27	1.0006	1023.86	0.8719
0.150	1027.73	1.1663	1026.46	1.0186	1025.05	0.8872
0.175	1028.92	1.1881	1027.65	1.0367	1026.24	0.9025
0.200	1030.11	1.2100	1028.84	1.0548	1027.43	0.9178

Fig. 1. Variation of viscosity (η) with molality (m) of L-arginine in (a) water, (b) 2% aq-MM, (c) 4% aq-MM and (d) 6% aq-MM, at different temperatures.

plot between $(\eta_r - 1)/m^{1/2}$ and $m^{1/2}$ (Fig. 2, Table 2) by least squares analysis, are found to be linear at all concentrations and temperatures.

As mentioned earlier, the viscosity B -coefficients provide useful information regarding the solvation of the solute and its effects on the structure of solvent in the surrounding of the solute molecules. The observed viscosity B -coefficients for L-arginine in water and aqueous-MM are positive indicating that the solute-solvent interactions are strong at all the studied molal concentrations and temperatures. The viscosity B -coefficients of L-arginine in 2.5%, 5% aqueous D-xylose; and 2.5%, 5% aqueous L-arabinose solutions at 298.15 K are 0.508, 0.582 and 0.525, 0.599 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), respectively, while in aqueous medium it has been reported as 0.404 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)¹⁹.

The viscosity B -coefficients of L-arginine in 0.5 M aqueous sucrose²⁸, 1.0 m aqueous glucose, 0.3 m aqueous sucrose, 0.3 m aqueous ascorbic acid¹⁷, 0.3 m aqueous galactose, 0.3 m aqueous maltose, 0.3 m aqueous lactose²⁹ solutions at the same temperature are reported as 0.826, 0.752, 0.731, 0.649, 0.763, 0.357, 0.348 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$), respectively.

An analysis of Table 2 reveals that, the values of viscosity B -coefficients for L-arginine in water agree very well with available literature value¹⁹ and positive viscosity B -coefficients for various L-arginine solutions are larger than in water indicating that in presence of co-solute (MM), the structure of solution gets strengthened. This means that when water is replaced by MM, the co-solute acts as structure-maker of water by hydrogen bond-

Fig. 2. Variation of $[(\eta_r - 1)/m^{1/2}]$ with molality (m) of L-arginine in (a) water, (b) 2% aq-MM, (c) 4% aq-MM and (d) 6% aq-MM, at different temperatures.

Table 2. Viscosity B -coefficients, viscosity B -coefficients of transfer (B_{tr}) and temperature coefficients (dB/dT) of L-arginine at different temperatures

Solvent	Viscosity B -coefficients ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) / Viscosity B -coefficients of transfer ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)			dB/dT ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)
	T (K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	
Water	0.465	0.407	0.378	-0.009
2% aq-MM solution	0.570/ 0.105	0.517/ 0.110	0.488/ 0.110	-0.008
4% aq-MM solution	0.700/ 0.235	0.652/ 0.245	0.613/ 0.235	-0.009
6% aq-MM solution	0.841/ 0.376	0.792/ 0.385	0.766/ 0.388	-0.008

ing. An increase in viscosity B -coefficients with increase in increasing concentration of MM (Fig. 3) may be due to increase in friction that may prevent flow of from water at increased concentration of maltose monohydrate. Thus, the inference drawn from viscosity B -coefficients supports the behaviour of existence of strong solute-solvent interactions in comparison to solute-solute interactions.

Fig. 3. Variation of Jones-Dole coefficient (B) with temperature (T) of L-arginine in water and aq-MM.

The viscosity B -coefficients also decrease with increase in temperature (Fig. 3) implying that hydration effects are sensitive to the temperature variations. An important information regarding structure-making or structure-breaking capability of the solute in solvent system is well documented by considering the temperature derivative of the viscosity B -coefficients, dB/dT ^{25,30}. Our result (Table 2) shows that dB/dT is negative which suggests that L-arginine acts as structure maker in aqueous-MM system. The structure-making ability of L-arginine in aqueous-D-xylose and aqueous-L-arabinose solutions has also been observed by Nain *et al.*¹⁹. The viscosity B -coefficients of transfer, B_{tr} , of L-arginine from water to aqueous-MM has been evaluated using the relation :

$$B_{tr} = B_{aq-MM} - B_{water} \quad (2)$$

where B_{water} is the viscosity B -coefficients of L-arginine in water. B_{tr} values are calculated by taking the difference between viscosity B -coefficients in aqueous-MM and

in water for each studied concentration. The B_{tr} values reported in Table 2 and the increase in B_{tr} values with the increase in concentration (Fig. 4) is due to interactions of MM with either R groups or charged centers of L-arginine. In other words the main contribution to viscosity B -coefficients of transfer values comes from the interactions between charged centers of L-arginine and MM molecules, rather than from interactions between R groups of L-arginine and MM molecules causing an increase in viscosity and thus in B -coefficient. Similar results are available in literature^{22,31}.

Fig. 4. Variation of viscosity B -coefficients of transfer (B_{tr}), with mass % of MM for L-arginine in aq-MM, at different temperatures.

Thermodynamics of viscous flow :

According to transition state theory^{32,33}, each and every solvent molecule in one mole of solution must be accompanied by transition, which may bond less or more strongly with solute molecules. Hence, the Gibbs free energy of activation or chemical potential per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{o\#}$, can be obtained using the following relation³².

$$\eta_o = \left(\frac{hN_A}{V_1^o} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_1^{o\#}}{RT} \right) \quad (3)$$

which upon rearrangement gives :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{o\#} = RT \ln \left(\frac{\eta_o V_1^o}{hN_A} \right) \quad (4)$$

where N_A , h , R and T are Avogadro's number, Planck's constant, universal gas constant and temperature, respec-

tively. V_1° is the apparent or partial molar volume of aqueous maltose monohydrate (solvent) which is calculated from density data at different temperatures using relation as : $V_1^\circ = M/\rho_0$. It has also been postulated, on the basis of transition state theory of the relative viscosity, by Feakins *et al.*^{33,34} that the activation Gibbs free energy, $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#}$, may be related to viscosity B -coefficients.

$$B = \frac{(V_1^\circ - V_2^\circ) + V_1^\circ(\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#})/RT}{1000} \quad (5)$$

Rearrangement of above equation gives rise to activation Gibbs free energy for viscous flow per mole of the solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$, i.e.

$$\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#} + \left(\frac{RT}{V_1^\circ}\right)[1000 - B(V_1^\circ - V_2^\circ)] \quad (6)$$

Here, $V_2^\circ = V_1^\circ$, is the limiting apparent or partial molar volume of the solute. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#}$, V_1° and $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$ thus obtained are listed in Table 3. The values of $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$ are large and positive than those of $\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#}$ in L-arginine in aqueous and aqueous-MM system reflecting that interaction between L-arginine and aqueous-MM in

the ground state is stronger than in the transition state. In other words, formation of transition state is less favoured in presence of L-arginine. This means that the formation of transition state is accompanied by the rupture and distortion of intermolecular forces in aqueous-MM structure. However, the decrease in solute-solvent interactions becomes apparent when the system is subjected to increase in temperature. Similar results were also reported by Pal and Kumar³⁵. This is clear from $\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$ values which decrease as the temperature is increased from 298.15 K to 308.15 K (Fig. 5), thus making the flow easier³⁶.

The activation entropy, $\Delta S_2^{\circ\#}$, and activation enthalpy, $\Delta H_2^{\circ\#}$ for the viscous flow of L-arginine in water and aqueous-MM solutions have been obtained by using the following equations.

$$\Delta S_2^{\circ\#} = -\left(\frac{d\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}}{dT}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta H_2^{\circ\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#} + T\Delta S_2^{\circ\#} \quad (8)$$

The calculated values of $\Delta H_2^{\circ\#}$ and $\Delta S_2^{\circ\#}$ for L-arginine are temperature-dependent, that may be due to the competition between various interactions taking place in these solutions. The obtained activation parameters are listed

Table 3. Apparent (partial) molar volume of solvent (V_1°), Gibbs free energy of activation for solvent ($\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#}$), Gibbs free energy of activation for solution ($\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$), $\Delta S_2^{\circ\#}$, activation enthalpy ($\Delta H_2^{\circ\#}$) of L-arginine in water, aqueous-MM (2 to 6 mass % of MM in water) solutions at different temperatures

T (K)	$V_1^\circ \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$\Delta\mu_1^{\circ\#}$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta\mu_2^{\circ\#}$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta S_2^{\circ\#}$ ($\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	$\Delta H_2^{\circ\#}$ (kJ mol^{-1})
(i) L-Arginine in water					
298.15	18.07	9.16	87.30	-1.009	-213.53
303.15	18.09	9.04	80.35	-1.009	-225.53
308.15	18.12	8.93	77.21	-1.009	-233.71
(ii) L-Arginine 2% aq-MM solution					
298.15	18.29	9.32	100.99	-0.889	-164.07
303.15	18.30	9.19	95.04	-0.889	-174.46
308.15	18.32	9.05	92.10	-0.889	-181.85
(iii) L-Arginine 4% aq-MM solution					
298.15	18.51	9.47	117.38	-0.894	-149.17
303.15	18.53	9.33	112.48	-0.894	-158.54
308.15	18.55	9.17	108.44	-0.894	-167.05
(iv) L-Arginine 6% aq-MM solution					
298.15	18.72	9.63	135.11	-0.671	-64.95
303.15	18.74	9.47	130.24	-0.671	-73.17
308.15	18.77	9.28	128.40	-0.671	-78.37

Fig. 5. Variation of Gibbs free energy of activation per mole of the solute ($\Delta\mu_2^\circ\#$) with temperature (T) of L-arginine in water and aq-MM.

in Table 3. Further, the values of $\Delta H_2^\circ\#$ and $\Delta S_2^\circ\#$, are negative which indicates that the formation of transition state is associated with bond making and increase in order which support the results as discussed earlier.

Conclusions

The viscosities, η , of solutions using different molalities L-arginine in water and in aqueous-maltose monohydrate at various concentrations as 2%, 4% and 6% are measured and are reported at different temperatures. Using the experimental viscometric data various transport and activation parameters, viz. the viscosity B -coefficients, viscosity B -coefficients of transfer, variation of B with temperature, the Gibbs free energy of activation of viscous flow per mole of solvent as well as per mole of solute, activation entropy and activation enthalpy, were calculated and reported. The observed positive viscosity B -coefficients values for various L-arginine solutions show that the interactions get strengthened in presence of MM indicating the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. The temperature dependence of coefficient data (dB/dT) values come out to be negative which shows that L-arginine act as structure-maker in aqueous-MM solution. The data is supported by considering the thermodynamic parameters.

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